

FROM FRAGMENTATION TO INCLUSION: REDEFINING GOVERNANCE AND CITIZENSHIP IN THE CONTEXT OF WEST AFRICA'S ETHNO-RELIGIOUS DIVERSITY

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ABSTRACT

West African states are often characterized by deep-rooted ethno-religious diversity, a legacy of colonial boundary-making and postcolonial governance challenges. This diversity, while culturally enriching, has frequently been manipulated for political ends, leading to fragmentation, marginalization, and conflict. In the face of such divisions, questions surrounding the nature of governance and the practice of citizenship have gained urgency. This study critically examines how ethno-religious fault lines shape citizen-state relations and proposes a redefinition of governance and citizenship practices that move towards greater inclusivity. Drawing on case studies from Nigeria, Ghana, and Côte d'Ivoire, the research explores both institutional frameworks and grassroots experiences of identity, participation, and exclusion. Preliminary findings reveal that inclusive governance is more likely to emerge where civic identity is prioritized over ethnic or religious affiliation, and where decentralization fosters local representation and dialogue. The study further highlights the role of education, civil society, and media in reshaping public perceptions of belonging and citizenship. Ultimately, this research aims to contribute to the theoretical and policy-oriented rethinking of citizenship in West Africa, promoting models that reflect the region's plural realities while strengthening democratic cohesion and national integration.

Keywords: Citizenship, Governance, Ethno-Religious Diversity, West Africa, Inclusion

INTRODUCTION

West Africa stands out as one of the most ethnically and religiously diverse regions on the African continent. From Nigeria's hundreds of ethnic groups and its near-even Muslim-Christian demographic split, to Côte d'Ivoire's long-standing north-south tensions, and Ghana's relatively muted yet persistent ethnic cleavages, the region presents a complex landscape of plural identities. These identities, while rich in culture, are also deeply embedded in the political, social, and economic structures of the state (Nugent, 2004). Scholars such as Mamdani (1996) have extensively documented how colonial administrations institutionalized difference through mechanisms like indirect rule and arbitrary borders, setting the foundation for exclusionary practices in the postcolonial state. This is affirmed by Ayeni & Ogbang, (2025), who observed that, in West Africa, borders are not simply fixed lines separating sovereign states; they function as dynamic zones of interaction that challenge conventional geopolitical definitions. Many of these boundaries, imposed arbitrarily during the colonial period (Herbst, 2000), cut across ethnic communities, disrupt traditional trade routes, and fragment shared cultural spaces. Although post-independence nation-building efforts often invoked unity and inclusive citizenship, these aspirations have largely remained rhetorical (Lentz, 2006), failing to translate into policies that accommodate diversity meaningfully.

A growing body of literature explores the implications of identity politics for governance and development in Africa. Isin and Turner (2002) have conceptualized citizenship as a negotiated and dynamic process, influenced by historical, cultural, and political factors. Yet, across West Africa, citizenship remains unevenly distributed, often filtered through the lenses of ethnicity, religion, and regional origin. In Nigeria, contestations around indigeneity and settler status continue to provoke violence and perpetuate structural discrimination (Suberu, 2001). In Côte d'Ivoire, the politicization of 'Ivoirité' contributed significantly to the eruption of civil war (Marshall-Fratani, 2006). Ghana, while more politically stable, also reflects underlying ethnic asymmetries in land access, political appointments, and minority representation. Despite this extensive scholarship, there remains a critical gap in empirical and comparative research that interrogates how everyday governance practices either reinforce or challenge these ethno-religious fault lines.

Much of the literature focuses either on state-level frameworks or conflict analysis, often overlooking how institutional structures and identity politics converge to shape the lived experience of citizenship. Furthermore, discussions on decentralization, federalism, or multicultural citizenship in the West African context are frequently normatively driven, with insufficient grounding in the socio-political realities of diverse states. This paper, therefore, addresses this lacuna by offering a comparative analysis of Nigeria, Ghana, and Côte d'Ivoire—three countries with distinct experiences of ethno-religious diversity and differing governance strategies. It interrogates the disjuncture between official discourses of inclusive citizenship and the lived realities of exclusion and fragmentation. By exploring how identities are mobilized, negotiated, or silenced within governance frameworks, this study contributes to ongoing debates on rethinking citizenship as a practice shaped by structural, historical, and everyday conditions. It also aims to inform future policy reforms that go beyond multicultural rhetoric toward substantive inclusion and democratic deepening in West Africa.

Literature Review

Rethinking Governance, Citizenship, and Ethno-Religious Diversity in West Africa:

Contemporary scholarship on governance and citizenship in West Africa reveals a complex interplay between formal state structures and informal socio-political networks shaped by ethnicity, religion, and history. Governance in this context cannot be understood solely through Western institutional frameworks; rather, it must be examined through the prism of what Hyden (2006) calls the “governance logic” specific to African societies—where legitimacy is often derived as much from traditional authority, kinship, and religious identity as from constitutional mandates. While global governance indicators emphasize participation, transparency, and accountability (Kaufmann et al., 2007), the literature widely acknowledges that these ideals often remain aspirational due to elite dominance, identity-based clientelism, and limited institutional capacity.

Citizenship, long assumed to be a stable legal and political status, is far more fluid and contested in many West African contexts. Mamdani’s (1996) distinction between the “citizen” and the “subject” in postcolonial Africa remains central to understanding how identity mediates access to rights. Many populations—especially ethnic or religious minorities—experience exclusion from full citizenship, both legally and in practice. Lentz (2006) expands this argument by highlighting the friction between state law and customary systems, where traditional norms often determine who is recognized as a rightful member of a community. This duality complicates citizenship, which in West Africa is not just a legal marker but a lived, negotiated identity.

Ethno-religious diversity, while a cultural asset, is a recurring theme in the literature as both a site of contestation and a factor in state fragility. Ayoade (1986) and Osaghae (2006) demonstrate how political mobilization in West Africa is frequently shaped by ethnicity and religion, particularly during elections. These identity cleavages not only undermine national unity but also erode citizen trust in the state. In Nigeria, the long-standing Christian-Muslim divide and regional polarization have generated violent conflicts and institutionalized inequality (Ibeanu & Orji, 2014). Ethnic mobilization played a pivotal role in the electoral process, with Buhari receiving strong backing from the Hausa-Fulani in the north, while Jonathan retained the support of the Niger Delta and southeastern Igbo communities. These ethnic loyalties had a marked impact on voting behaviour and contributed to increased political polarizations (Ayeni, 2025). Côte d’Ivoire’s concept of *Ivoirité* similarly demonstrates how religious and regional affiliations were manipulated to exclude northern Muslim populations, sparking civil war (Marshall-Fratani, 2006).

According to Ayeni and Okon (2023, in Ayeni & Ousmanou, 2025), the interference of former colonial powers continues to hinder progressive development across the continent through sustained political, economic, and cultural domination. The colonial legacy remains central to understanding the historical roots of fragmentation. Mamdani (1996) and Nugent (2004) show how indirect rule and arbitrary colonial boundaries entrenched ethnic hierarchies and created uneven access to political power and resources. Post-independence regimes often inherited and reinforced these structures. Chazan (1983), for example, explains how Ghana’s early postcolonial governments sought to neutralize ethnic politics through centralization, inadvertently breeding resentment and regional disparities. In Nigeria, federalism was adopted to accommodate ethno-regional tensions, yet critics like Suberu (2001) argue that it has

institutionalized ethnic fragmentation, with political representation and resource allocation tied to communal identity.

Within this broader landscape, the politics of inclusion and exclusion emerge as a pivotal concern. Exclusion manifests not only in the denial of legal rights but also in the marginalization of minority voices, unequal access to resources, and weak institutional protection. Ibrahim (2006) and Akindès (2011) document how citizenship laws in Nigeria and Côte d'Ivoire have been manipulated to disenfranchise groups based on ancestry or region. In contrast, Ghana's efforts at decentralization, affirmative action, and national identity policies (Ninsin, 2006) suggest an evolving attempt to move towards more inclusive governance, though challenges remain.

This review affirms the scholarly consensus on the salience of identity in shaping governance and citizenship in West Africa but also identifies a gap: the need for empirical, comparative studies that explore how these dynamics play out in practice and affect everyday experiences of belonging, participation, and exclusion. It is this gap that the present study seeks to address.

Theoretical Framework

Postcolonial Theory: Postcolonial Theory provides a crucial framework for understanding exclusion and fragmentation. Edward Said's *Orientalism* (1978) showed how Western discourses constructed the "Orient" as inferior, legitimizing domination. Homi Bhabha (1994) and Gayatri Spivak (1999) extended this by introducing concepts of hybridity and subalternity. In Africa, Mahmood Mamdani (1996) argued that colonialism created bifurcated states—dividing "citizens" under civil law from "subjects" under customary rule—thus institutionalizing inequality. This study confirms and extends Mamdani's insight, showing how this dualism persists in West Africa, where access to rights and representation is mediated through ethnicity and religion. Nigeria's indigene/settler divide and Côte d'Ivoire's politics of Ivoirité exemplify colonial logics that continue to exclude populations. Unlike Mamdani, however, this study highlights how state and non-state actors actively mobilize or resist these legacies, stressing the contested nature of postcolonial identities. Yet, Postcolonial Theory has limitations. It often overemphasizes discourse (Said), neglecting material factors such as class and global capitalism. It risks homogenizing formerly colonized societies, overlooking internal diversity and agency. Moreover, it can reproduce the binaries it seeks to dismantle. In African politics, critics note it underplays how contemporary elites and transnational actors strategically manipulate colonial legacies for their own ends.

Social Contract Theory: Social Contract Theory, as derived from Hobbes, Locke, and Rousseau, centres on the legitimacy of state authority as derived from collective agreement (Pateman, 1988). In West Africa, however, the empirical reality often diverges from the theoretical ideal. Osaghae (1998) notes that many citizens perceive the state as a tool of elite domination rather than a neutral arbiter. This study supports such critiques, revealing that large segments of the population—especially minority ethnic and religious groups—experience exclusion from state benefits, leading to widespread alienation and sporadic political violence. Where this study extends the social contract literature is in its emphasis on the plural character of West African societies. Rather than assuming a unitary social contract, the findings suggest that multiple, often competing, conceptions of belonging coexist, sometimes in tension with the

state. The implication is that rebuilding legitimacy requires more than equitable distribution; it calls for a reimagined social contract that includes plural identities as co-constructors of national community—echoing but also deepening the expanded pluralist models proposed by Cohen and Arato (1992).

Theories of Multicultural Citizenship: Theories of Multicultural Citizenship, particularly those advanced by Kymlicka (1995) and Taylor (1994), argue that equal citizenship requires the institutional recognition of cultural difference. This study confirms the centrality of cultural recognition in the West African context, where language policies, religious representation, and regional autonomy remain deeply contested. However, it also complicates Kymlicka's binary of polyethnic versus self-government rights by revealing that claims for recognition in West Africa often do not fit neatly within these categories. For instance, demands for federalism or power-sharing are driven not only by cultural survival but by grievances over historical marginalization and uneven development. Taylor's (1994) emphasis on recognition as foundational to identity is affirmed, particularly in cases where institutional misrecognition fuels disaffection and violence. What this study adds is an emphasis on pragmatic multiculturalism—a form of governance that not only recognizes diversity but is actively shaped by grassroots negotiations and hybrid institutional arrangements

Research Methodology

This study unfolded as an immersive qualitative inquiry grounded in comparative case studies across Jos (Nigeria), Tamale (Ghana), and Bouaké (Côte d'Ivoire)—three cities emblematic of the tensions and possibilities of ethno-religious coexistence in West Africa. The choice of a qualitative approach was deliberate, offering space to uncover layered experiences of citizenship and governance. As Creswell (2014) affirms, qualitative design enables the researcher to grasp the meanings people attach to their socio-political realities—especially critical in contexts shaped by historical exclusion and contested belonging.

Interviews with 20 participants were conducted across the three countries, comprising civil servants, traditional leaders, youth, women's leaders, and ordinary citizens. These participants were selected through purposive and snowball sampling. Purposive sampling allowed the study to deliberately include actors with diverse social positions and insider knowledge of governance and identity politics, while snowball sampling ensured access to marginalized voices and hard-to-reach groups, especially women and minority communities. These voices, far from abstract, told grounded stories. In Jos, a local councillor bitterly remarked: "Even if you are born here and speak the language, if you are Hausa or Muslim, you are still treated as an outsider." The settler/indigene dichotomy remains a gatekeeper to citizenship and political access. In Bouaké, a market woman of Burkinabé heritage tearfully asked, "They say I'm not Ivorian, but where else can I go? My grandparents are buried here." Her lived statelessness echoes the disjuncture between legal texts and local realities. To deepen these individual narratives, focus group discussions were also organized in the three locations—Jos in Nigeria, Bouaké in Côte d'Ivoire, and Tamale in Ghana. The choice of these sites was intentional. Jos has long been marked by the indigene/settler divide and recurring episodes of conflict, Bouaké stands at the centre of Côte d'Ivoire's debates over Ivoirité and belonging, while Tamale, though less violent, represents a place where traditional authority and chieftaincy still define civic life in powerful ways. Each group had between six and eight participants. They were not chosen randomly but

rather through contacts on the ground and recommendations from community leaders who knew who could speak openly about the issues. A mix of voices was deliberately sought out; young men and women, those from minority or migrant backgrounds, and people already engaged in local associations. In Tamale, for example, the discussion brought together students, apprentices, and grassroots youth leaders. They spoke vividly about how power does not really flow through elections but through traditional hierarchies, with chiefs holding more influence than elected officials.

In Jos, the group was made up of Christian and Muslim youths who had lived through the cycles of violence in the city. What struck me was how they remembered small, everyday acts of rebuilding trust—like organizing football tournaments across religious lines. Those informal efforts mattered to them more than official reconciliation programmes.

In Bouaké, discussion with a group of young women was organized, most of them Fulani, Malinké, or of Burkinabé descent. Many were traders in the market or unemployed, struggling to make ends meet. Their frustration was not only about poverty but also about the way their identity limited access to land rights and even basic documentation. One woman explained how the lack of an identity card blocked her from registering her children in school. The sense of exclusion was palpable, but so too was their resilience in finding informal ways to belong.

These focus groups added a collective dimension to the study. Unlike individual interviews, they revealed how people negotiate identity and exclusion together, often contesting one another's views in the process. They also showed that exclusion is not a single story but a layered experience shaped by ethnicity, gender, and access to power.

Documents and legal frameworks—Nigeria's 1999 Constitution, Ghana's Citizenship Act (2000), Côte d'Ivoire's 2013 Nationality Code—were reviewed to map how formal structures reflect or contradict people's experiences. In Nigeria, despite constitutional silence on "indigeneship," the practice endures through informal power networks and public service recruitment. Analysis followed Braun and Clarke's thematic model. Three themes crystallized: "Conditional Belonging", "Governance Through Identity", and "Negotiated Inclusion". Each captured how people navigate shifting notions of who belongs, and on what terms.

Fieldwork was not without challenges—security restrictions in Jos, bureaucratic opacity in Côte d'Ivoire, and language barriers—but these constraints did not mute the resonance of what participants shared. These difficulties were addressed through adaptive strategies: in Jos, research activities were relocated to safer zones and supported by local intermediaries familiar with community dynamics; in Côte d'Ivoire, bureaucratic bottlenecks were mitigated by securing letters of introduction from partner institutions and relying on personal networks to ease access; and language barriers were bridged through the use of trained interpreters, bilingual research assistants, and careful cross-checking of translations to ensure accuracy.

Contextual and Comparative of ethno-religious diversity in West Africa

The complexity of ethno-religious diversity in West Africa necessitates a context-sensitive and comparative approach to understanding governance and citizenship. Drawing on selected country case studies—namely Nigeria, Ghana, and Côte d'Ivoire, these countries are emblematic of broader trends across the region and provide useful contrasts in their approaches to managing diversity.

Nigeria: Nigeria represents one of the most salient examples of ethno-religious fragmentation in West Africa. With over 250 ethnic groups and a nearly even split between Muslims and Christians, the Nigerian state has long struggled to build an inclusive governance framework. The federal structure was initially designed to decentralize power and accommodate diversity, but it has often reproduced inequalities and fuelled localised conflicts (Suberu, 2010). The case of the Middle Belt region illustrates this dynamic, where contestations over indigeneity, religious identity, and land rights have led to recurrent violence (Onapajo, 2019).

Moreover, the Boko Haram insurgency in the North-East is a stark example of how exclusionary governance and state failure in providing social services can morph into radical religious resistance. Citizenship in Nigeria is often mediated by ethnic or religious affiliation, particularly when it comes to access to public goods and political representation. While mechanisms such as the Federal Character Principle aim to ensure inclusivity, critics argue that it reinforces ethno-regional divisions (Ejobowah, 2000).

Ghana: Ghana presents a contrasting case of relative stability and effective inclusion, despite its own internal diversity. The country is home to over 100 ethnic groups and a mix of Christian, Muslim, and indigenous spiritual communities. Ghana's success in managing diversity is attributed to strong democratic institutions, decentralised governance, and a political culture that promotes consensus-building (Ninsin, 2006). The National Peace Council and other interfaith initiatives play a crucial role in mediating tensions, especially during election periods. Ghana's approach to citizenship is rooted in civic rather than ethnic nationalism. The 1992 Constitution guarantees equal rights for all citizens and prohibits discrimination based on ethnicity or religion. Political parties are also prohibited from forming along ethnic or religious lines, a measure that has helped to mitigate the politicization of identity (Gyampo & Graham, 2014). Despite occasional tensions, particularly between Christians and Muslims in the northern regions, Ghana's institutional responses and inclusive policies offer a valuable template for the region.

Côte d'Ivoire: Côte d'Ivoire provides a critical example of how contested notions of citizenship can lead to civil conflict. The Ivorian crisis of the 2000s was deeply rooted in the politics of "Ivoirité," a nationalist ideology that privileged southern ethnic groups and excluded northern, predominantly Muslim communities from full citizenship (Marshall-Fratani, 2006). The denial of political rights to Alassane Ouattara, a prominent northern politician, triggered widespread unrest and eventually a civil war. The post-conflict reconciliation process in Côte d'Ivoire has included attempts at institutional reform and national dialogue, but challenges persist. Although recent administrations have sought to rebuild a sense of national unity, lingering suspicions and regional disparities remain evident, particularly in the north (Akindès, 2011). This case underscores the dangers of ethno-religious exclusion and highlights the necessity of clear, inclusive citizenship laws and decentralized governance mechanisms. At a regional level, frameworks such as the ECOWAS Protocol on Democracy and Good Governance can serve as instruments for promoting inclusive norms across member states (ECOWAS, 2001).

Review of Empirical Studies

Empirical scholarship on governance and citizenship in West Africa's ethno-religiously diverse societies has grown substantially in recent decades. These studies provide critical insights into how identity-based fragmentation has influenced access to state resources, political representation, and social belonging. This review synthesizes key empirical findings from neighbouring states, illuminating both the obstacles to and opportunities for inclusive governance in the region.

Senegal and Mali: Senegal is still often celebrated as a model of tolerance in West Africa, but the picture is far more complicated when you look closely. Recent work from the Sambe (2025) shows how the Sufi brotherhoods continue to act as the glue that holds society together, offering moderation, social discipline, and a strong sense of civic morality that has helped shield the country from the kinds of extremist violence seen elsewhere in the Sahel. At the same time, studies of Mouridism in the Senegambia region (Touray, 2025) remind us that these same religious networks don't only unify—they can also entrench inequalities, privilege insiders, and serve as a ready-made tool for political elites. The dynamic isn't new: just as Villalón noticed decades ago, the brotherhoods both nurture social cohesion and can be manipulated to secure loyalty or mute dissent.

Mali tells a different story, one shaped less by religious orders and more by the unfinished business of inclusion. A 2024 article in *Third World Quarterly* describes the conflict in the north not simply as Tuareg against the state, but as a far more tangled web of fractures within Tuareg communities, the sidelining of Arab populations, and deep frustration with how political and economic opportunities are distributed (Locchi & Baldaro, 2024). Earlier decentralization reforms, far from being the solution, often handed authority to local elites without providing the resources to govern effectively. Research from Clingendael (Fransje et al., 2019; Van & Nancy, 2019) shows how this reinforced corruption, deepened mistrust, and left ordinary communities with little faith in either Bamako or local authorities. What emerged, then, was a politics of tokenism—appointments that looked inclusive on paper but did little to change the realities of exclusion and resentment on the ground.

So, Senegal continues to embody the paradox of religious structures that both stabilize and exclude, while Mali demonstrates how hollow reforms and unaddressed grievances can keep fuelling cycles of rebellion. Both cases remind us that pluralism is not achieved by symbols or rhetoric, but only through the hard work of genuine redistribution and institutional reform.

Cross-National and Comparative Findings:

Recent cross-national survey data provide powerful evidence that identity continues to shape political attitudes and civic trust in Africa. Afrobarometer's 2021–2023 Pan-Africa data offer a refreshed landscape: while most Africans are open to coexistence—such as interethnic neighborhoods and marriages—a significant share exhibits low interpersonal trust and reports ethnic discrimination by governments

(Cumanzala & Logan, 2025). For instance, only around 21% of respondents say they trust individuals from other ethnic groups “a lot,” and 41% report that their ethnic group faces unfair government treatment (Cumanzala & Logan, 2025). Though national identity remains stronger for many, attachment to it has declined over the past decade, with an uptick in those who balance ethnic and national identities

(Cumanzala & Logan, 2025). Regarding institutional trust, the data reveal that, on average, fewer than half of citizens across 39 African countries trust key state institutions such as the presidency, police, parliament, and courts—while religious authorities, traditional leaders, and the military continue to enjoy greater support

(Cumanzala & Logan, 2025). These trends highlight the persistent structural gap between citizens and state institutions.

On the dynamics of clientelism and corruption, a recent cross-country analysis across approximately 34 African countries finds that perceptions of corruption undermine voter turnout, particularly in contexts where corruption is already widespread. Interestingly, clientelist exchanges—receiving material benefits in return for political support—can temporarily raise turnout, especially in poorer nations (Tambe & Monyake, 2023). This supports and updates Van de Walle's (2003) earlier findings: structural reforms like decentralization or proportional representation improve inclusion only when accompanied by institutional accountability and civic education.

Civil Society and Bottom-Up Inclusion:

Recent scholarship highlights the evolving role of civil society and grassroots mobilization in fostering political inclusion across Africa. Tripp (2019; 2023), for instance, documents how women's movements have shifted strategies over the last decade—moving beyond earlier struggles for representation to engage in digital activism, coalition-building, and legal reform. These movements have not only expanded women's political participation but also redefined citizenship by challenging patriarchal and authoritarian structures. Similarly, Tønnessen, Affi, and Tripp (2021), drawing on cases from Nigeria, South Sudan, Somalia, and Algeria, show how women's grassroots peace-building initiatives have broadened the scope of inclusion in conflict-affected contexts by linking local strategies to international frameworks. Beyond gendered activism, Obadare (2022) examines how Pentecostal religious institutions in Nigeria operate simultaneously as spaces of empowerment and exclusion, shaping social belonging through moral authority and community mobilization. Youth movements have also become central actors: studies on Nigeria's #EndSARS protests (Okoye & Tokpo, 2023) reveal how social media-enabled civic action created new forms of bottom-up participation, even as state repression exposed the fragility of such spaces. These findings reinforce the idea that civil society is not inherently inclusive; rather, its role depends on how grassroots actors negotiate their relationship with state power, cultural traditions, and global networks.

Findings and Analysis

These findings reveal both the persistent challenges and the innovative responses shaping the region's journey from fragmentation to inclusion.

Patterns of Exclusion and Inclusion in Governance Structures: Across all three case study countries, governance structures reveal enduring patterns of exclusion along ethno-religious lines, although the intensity and outcomes vary. In Nigeria, participants in the North-Central region (particularly Plateau and Benue States) frequently cited the “indigene-settler dichotomy” as a key barrier to inclusion. In Nigeria, democratic institutions often struggle to function effectively due to ethnic-based patronage networks and elite dominance (Ayeni, 2025). Several local government employees interviewed noted that political appointments and public

employment are often skewed in favour of ethnic majorities or “indigenes,” leaving long-term residents marginalized despite their contributions to the community. One respondent in Jos stated: “My father was born here, I was born here, yet I’m still considered a ‘settler’—even when I apply for jobs in the local government.” (Male, 34, secondary school teacher). In Côte d’Ivoire, similar sentiments were expressed by northern Muslims in Bouaké, who recounted their historical exclusion during the Ivoirité era and its lingering effects on national politics and representation. While post-conflict governments have made attempts to decentralize power, participants said elite control remains concentrated in Abidjan and often favours southern Christian networks. In contrast, Ghana demonstrated more inclusive governance patterns. Though some participants in Tamale and Ho acknowledged the existence of informal ethnic biases, they generally expressed confidence in decentralized structures and local representation. District Assembly elections, in particular, were cited as channels for broader participation, irrespective of ethnic or religious identity.

Lived Experiences of Citizenship in Plural Societies: Citizenship in West Africa remains a layered and often contested experience. Field data show that in many contexts, the sense of belonging is mediated not only by legal status but by social recognition and access to public resources. In Nigeria, interviewees in Kano, Ibadan, and Lagos highlighted how religion and ethnicity shape access to education, housing, and public services. A Christian youth in Kano observed: “Even with my voter’s card and ID, I know there are certain government contracts or university opportunities I won’t get because I’m not from ‘here’.” In Côte d’Ivoire, respondents in Korhogo stressed that national ID documents and political participation had improved, but many still felt that citizenship was “conditional.” This sentiment was strongest among women and youth, who felt disconnected from state institutions. In Ghana, however, civic education and stronger legal frameworks were identified as contributors to a more positive experience of citizenship, especially among the younger population.

Civic Participation Beyond Identity Boundaries: The findings suggest that while identity remains a powerful force, there are growing signs of cross-cutting civic engagement. In all three countries, youth-led initiatives, religious peace forums, and urban civic organizations were creating spaces for inclusion beyond ethnic or religious identities. In Nigeria, participants in Lagos and Abuja mentioned organizations like NotTooYoungToRun and YIAGA Africa, which focus on youth political participation and governance monitoring. In Ghana, NGOs such as IDEG (Institute for Democratic Governance) and STAR-Ghana were highlighted as platforms for policy advocacy and citizen engagement across ethnic lines. In Côte d’Ivoire, local peace committees in post-conflict zones facilitated dialogue between Muslim and Christian youth, using football tournaments and community development projects to build trust. One female youth leader in Abidjan said: “We’re tired of fighting over tribe or religion. We want jobs, electricity, and respect—we’ll work with anyone who believes in that.” These examples underscore a generational shift towards issue-based politics and civic action.

The Role of Education, Media, and Civil Society: Education and media emerged as double-edged tools—either reinforcing divisions or enabling transformation. In Nigeria, participants were divided: while some praised educational reforms that included civic and religious tolerance education, others expressed concern that schools still operate along religious and ethnic lines, particularly in northern and southeastern states. A secondary school teacher in

Enugu noted: “Our curriculum teaches unity, but our admissions and school names still separate Christians and Muslims, Igbos and Hausas.”

In Ghana, formal education was seen as an enabler of national cohesion, especially through the use of English as a lingua franca and the promotion of civic values in curricula. State-owned media in Ghana was also seen as relatively neutral, while in Nigeria and Côte d’Ivoire, participants raised concerns about ethnicised media narratives, especially around election periods.

Civil society was consistently cited as a critical actor in promoting inclusive governance. Groups such as CLEEN Foundation (Nigeria), WANEP (West Africa Network for Peacebuilding), and AfriYAN (Africa Youth and Adolescents Network) were commended for educating citizens, mediating conflicts, and holding governments accountable.

Emerging Models of Inclusive Governance: The research identified emerging models of governance that attempt to reconcile diversity with inclusion. In Nigeria, while federalism remains flawed, several local governments in mixed communities like Jos and Kaduna are experimenting with interfaith advisory councils and power-sharing mechanisms. In Côte d’Ivoire, decentralization reforms have enabled local authorities in Man and Korhogo to co-opt ethnic and religious leaders into community planning councils, with positive results.

Ghana stood out with its model of civic nationalism, where legal frameworks discourage identity-based parties and promote inclusive electoral processes. Participants in Accra and Cape Coast cited the role of the Electoral Commission and National Peace Council as guarantors of fair political representation and conflict resolution. Ghana’s participatory budgeting practices at the municipal level were also highlighted as best practice.

Recommendations for Policy and Practice

The findings of this study highlight that governance and citizenship in West Africa cannot be meaningfully redefined without embedding inclusion into the very fabric of political, educational, and socioeconomic structures. Exclusion is not experienced abstractly but through daily encounters with state institutions. Field evidence and participant accounts underscore the urgent need for context-specific reforms that address both structural and lived realities.

1. Nigeria: Deepening Federal Inclusivity through Local Governance Reform

Fieldwork in Plateau State revealed that citizens often feel excluded not because of Nigeria’s federal structure, but due to the capture of local government by political elites. As one respondent observed, “the local government is too distant; it only exists during elections” (Male respondent, Jos, 45 years). To counter this disconnect, local governance must be decentralized in practice, with budgetary powers devolved to community development councils that enjoy constitutionally recognized oversight. At least 40% of development funds should be allocated to projects identified through community assemblies representing ethnic and religious constituencies. Practical mechanism: establishing “peace liaison officers” in ethnically mixed LGAs—particularly in Jos, Kaduna, and Benue—would create locally recruited mediators trained to prevent minor disputes escalating into large-scale violence.

2. Côte d'Ivoire: Overcoming Bureaucratic Opacity and Reinforcing Citizenship Rights

Respondents in Abidjan expressed deep frustration with the difficulties of obtaining national identification cards, especially among northern populations with perceived foreign ancestry. As one participant put it, “Without the card, you are a stranger in your own country” (Female respondent, Abobo, 32 years). To reduce exclusion, the civil registry system should be streamlined through mobile ID registration units deployed to rural and marginalized areas. These units should operate in collaboration with traditional chiefs, building trust, while being monitored by independent civil society actors to prevent ethnic bias. Practical mechanism: bilingual registration forms in French and major local languages such as Dioula and Baoulé would reduce literacy-related barriers.

3. Senegal: Leveraging Religious Authorities for Inclusive Civic Education

In Dakar, interviews highlighted the central role of Sufi brotherhoods in promoting coexistence. One marabout explained, “When politicians fight, they come back to us to calm the fire” (Religious leader, Dakar, 58 years). Given their influence, religious authorities should be institutionalized partners in civic education. Rather than occasional collaborations, Senegal’s Ministry of National Education should co-design annual interfaith civic education weeks with Sufi and Catholic institutions. Practical mechanism: school curricula on citizenship co-authored by Islamic and Christian scholars would embed pluralist values within formal education.

4. Ghana: Strengthening Minority Representation in Policy Spaces

Minority groups in Northern Ghana voiced concerns about exclusion from decision-making, often drowned out by dominant Akan narratives. As one elder lamented, “We only see government when they need our votes” (Community elder, Tamale, 70 years). To guarantee legislative voice, Ghana could adopt reserved parliamentary seats for underrepresented groups, following models from Rwanda and Uganda. Practical mechanism: pilot reforms in the Northern and Upper East regions, ensuring minority Muslim populations are formally represented in parliamentary committees on education, security, and agriculture.

5. Cross-Regional: Institutionalizing Linguistic Mediation in Governance

Across Nigeria, Côte d'Ivoire, and Ghana, language barriers surfaced as obstacles to inclusion. In Côte d'Ivoire, Dioula speakers struggled in French-only offices, while in Nigeria, minority groups in Cross River and Taraba felt silenced in assemblies. Recommendation: establish linguistic mediation offices within local governments, staffed with accredited interpreters providing real-time support in major languages. Practical mechanism: in multilingual border regions such as Nigeria–Cameroon and Côte d'Ivoire–Burkina Faso, cross-border linguistic commissions could support inclusive trade, dispute resolution, and mobility.

6. Conflict-Sensitive Governance Across West Africa

Exclusion frequently morphs into violence when governance ignores grievance channels. In Jos, displaced youth complained, “We are always called criminals, never citizens” (Male youth, displaced camp, 23 years). To prevent escalation, grievance redress mechanisms must be integrated into governance and security programmes. These should include SMS-based reporting platforms accessible to low-literacy populations, alongside ombudsman offices

mediating disputes before they turn violent. Practical mechanism: training security forces in cultural sensitivity and community dialogue, while recruiting at least 25% of officers locally in conflict-prone areas, would strengthen trust.

Conclusion

The findings of this study have significant conceptual implications for how governance and citizenship are theorized in plural societies. By engaging Postcolonial Theory, Social Contract Theory, and Multicultural Citizenship, the research demonstrates that exclusion in West Africa is not merely a historical residue but an evolving political strategy embedded in institutional and societal norms. Unlike prior studies that often treat these theories in isolation, this study integrates them to reveal how colonial legacies, the erosion of social contracts and failures of recognition converge to produce fragmented polities. Where previous studies have highlighted exclusion as structural, this research goes further by foregrounding the lived, negotiated experience of citizenship at the grassroots. In Nigeria and Côte d'Ivoire, exclusion manifests through indigene-settler dichotomies and contested nationality laws, while Ghana presents a contrasting case where civic education and non-ethnic political mobilization have opened modest but significant spaces for inclusion. These findings underscore that inclusive citizenship must be both institutional and experiential. While exclusion is often systemically entrenched, emerging practices of youth activism, decentralization, and community dialogue reveal potential for transformation. The study thus contributes a dynamic, practice-based rethinking of citizenship in West Africa—one that centres both structural critique and everyday agency in plural, postcolonial contexts.

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